

SYMBOLIC EXPRESSION OF THE IDEA OF GOODNESS IN ARCHITECTURAL ESOTERIC DECORATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The Kokaldosh Madrasa is a memorial monument of the city of Tashkent. It was built by Qulbobo Kokaldosh in 1551–1575. It is located in the central Chorsu Square of Tashkent.

The roof of the madrasa is decorated with geometric ornament consisting of 10- and 5-pointed rakh patterns. Four squares on two sides are beautifully designed, depicting the charkhpalak (wheel of fortune) that is encountered in virtually all the architectural traditions of Central Asia. Until this century, no one has succeeded in scientifically analyzing this pattern. We have not yet found a scientific analysis in any source.

So, what wisdom do the four identical ornamental patterns on the facade of the Kokaldosh building embody?

Just as there is no meaningless word in the world, there is also no meaningless ornament.

If we look inside the square, it is divided into nine cells, and the words "Creator" and "Muhammad" are written four times in the Arabic alphabet. As shown in the figure, in side view, one large circle is depicted clockwise, while four smaller ones are shown counter-clockwise. In terms of color, the words Creator and Muhammad are rendered in the same color. Many people read the words Creator and Muhammad, but they cannot read these words and forms together. The reason for this is that people who know Arabic spelling do not know enough about the symbolic meaning of the forms, and even if they do, they find it difficult to read them together. In this article, we have determined the conceptual foundations of the composition of the epigraphic pattern and arrived at the following conclusion.

As a result of the astronomical study of the decorations of the Kokaldosh Madrasa, it has been established that the

program of human existence in the world is described through symbolic expressions based on the teachings of Islam.

The ancient land of Uzbekistan is rich in historical monuments. The cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva are the largest tourism centers of Central Asia. The capital of Uzbekistan — Tashkent, known in the 9th–10th centuries as Binkent — also possesses architectural monuments of the past. Binkent was surrounded by high walls and had 12 gates. The city walls were destroyed during the Mongol invasion, but were restored during the rule of Timur and the Timurids (14th–15th centuries), and Tashkent was transformed into a major feudal city with numerous beautiful buildings and structures. One of the most renowned architectural monuments of Tashkent is the Kokaldosh Madrasa.

The word "Kokaldosh" has two meanings:

1. Sworn brothers nursed by the same mother — that is, another's child whom a nanny nursed alongside her own. Such brothers of the padishah were given the nickname Kokaldosh. As indicated in "Ghiyas ul-Lughat" (Aid to Dictionaries), this word is formed from two Turkic words: "kuka" ("son of the nanny") and "tosh" or "dosh" ("companion"). The word "kuke" ("elder brother") is still used in the Kazakh language today.
2. In the Middle Ages in Turkestan — particularly in the Bukhara Khanate — an official responsible for ensuring the internal security of the country [1].

The madrasa was built by Qulbobo Kokaldosh in 1551–1575 on the central Chorsu Square of Tashkent. At the beginning of the 18th century, the madrasa building fell into decline and was converted into a caravanserai. Later it was restored. The masters who participated in the revival of the madrasa left the following inscription above the entrance gate: "This magnificent building was restored in the year 1246 of the Hijri calendar (1830–1831) by Azim Vali ugli usta Avaz Muhammad." Further one may read: "This building was reconstructed under the leadership of the chief palace commander Jahongirbek ugli Shodmonbek... Death of a person is inevitable, but his deeds remain forever." The majolica works were executed by the master Olimjon, son of master Salimjon" [2].

During the earthquake of 1868, the madrasa building was severely damaged, with the dome suffering particularly heavy damage. In 1902–1903, with funds collected by the people, the upper part of the madrasa was reconstructed, but the dome of the main facade and the facade itself were not restored.

The lateral sides of the facade up to the base of the dome and part of the ribbed walls were finished with European brick, and beautiful semicircular ravoki (front or inner part of the building in the form of a circle or niche) appeared next to the facade. Above the minarets — that is, small minarets were erected in the manner of mahalla mosques of the 18th–19th centuries. On the columns of the main facade, in place of the domes, lanterns of the same shape as those on the minarets were installed. During the earthquake of 1946, the madrasa was once again completely destroyed [3], and in the early 1950s it was reconstructed. On the facade of the madrasa, one can see geometric and five- and ten-sided patterns. On both sides of the facade are located two square ornaments and ornaments in the form of an altar-shelf (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Modern view of the Kokaldosh Madrasa.

On both sides there is also a finely finished square depicting the wheel of fortune (charkhpalak) that is encountered in the practice of all schools and traditions of Central Asian architecture. This ornament has not been examined in the scholarly literature.

Just as there are no words without meaning, there are also no ornaments without meaning. What, then, do the four identical square-shaped ornaments on the facade of the Kokaldosh Madrasa building signify?

Let us attempt to analyze this ornament.

Let us examine the square closely — it is divided into 9 cells, with the word "Creator" written in Arabic letters and the word "Muhammad" written four times. The inscriptions "Creator" and "Muhammad" are rendered in the same light-blue color. Many read these words but cannot perceive or analyze them in unity with the forms.

Figure 2. The symbolic ornament executed on both sides of the facade of the Kokaldosh Madrasa.

One large wheel of fortune is depicted moving clockwise, while four others move counter-clockwise.

Why was the square chosen? The square represents the four cardinal directions. It also signifies durability, the boundlessness of the universe, eternity, and light. It also denotes that man is a child of the Sun. In addition, the material foundation of the world consists of four elements: earth, water, air, and fire. The square is a symbol of symmetry, beauty, and equality (Figure 3).

The square is divided into 9 parts. If we inscribe numbers in the cells, we obtain an image as shown in Figure 4. Let us turn to the philosophy of numbers in mathematics: each number possesses a distinct logical and philosophical meaning. The number 1 signifies: Allah is one. The number 2 is a symbol of duality, and so on.

A human being develops in the mother's womb for 9 months, 9 days, 9 hours, and 9 minutes. A healthy person has 9 vital organs: eyes, ears, nose, mouth, hands, feet, abdomen, teeth, and tongue. In addition, the number 9 has been considered sacred since ancient times — a symbol of happiness.

At the center of the square is the number 5. A human being possesses five developed senses: hearing, sight, smell and taste, and touch. According to Eastern philosophy, earthly life is divided into five stages. A person comes to this transient world for trial, receives evaluation for their deeds, and after death awaits paradise or hell. Through this reminder, the artist wishes to call everyone to virtue. In addition, the number five denotes the five canons — the fundamental concepts of the Islamic religion: iman (faith in its broadest sense), namaz (prayer), uraza (fasting), almsgiving, and hajj. The symbolic meaning of the number five lies in the call to perform good deeds.

Рис. 3. Квадрат.

Он означает Вселенную. Материальная основа Вселенной состоит из четырех

Рис. 4. Квадрат на 9 равных частей.

Декор на фасаде медресе Кукалдаш.

Рис. 7. Аллах и Мухаммад.

Рис. 5.

Рис. 8. Обратное изображение

If we calculate the sum of the numbers vertically or horizontally, we obtain 6, 12, 18, 24.

In the holy book of Islam — the Qur'an — it is said that the Creator created 18,000 worlds in 6 days. The number 6 in Islamic philosophy is a symbol of perfection. In this verse, the number 6 is symbolic. It is stated here: "The Creator created 18,000 worlds in perfection." This implies that no human being can create anything better than the Creator.

The number 12 is likewise not coincidental. There are 12 months in a year. There are 24 hours in a day. The sum of the numbers along the diagonal equals 15. This signifies: a month contains 15 dark (difficult) days and 15 bright (good) days — that is, human life, like the cosmos, consists of light and darkness, and the life path of every human being is difficult.

On the square, the wheel of fortune is depicted in full clockwise rotation (Figure 5). The wheel of fortune is a symbol of eternal motion. This indicates that the world is in perpetual movement; movement toward goodness and happiness is an indispensable condition for the existence and development of the human personality. In addition, the word "chorunsur" (four elements) is used, meaning that the world consists of four elements: water, earth (soil), air, and fire. This form has been used in the East for more than 1,000 years with various meanings. The German mathematician Hermann Weyl wrote: the swastika is one of the most ancient symbols of humanity. Drawings on the walls of ancient Afrasiab, dating back to the 10th–11th centuries, confirm his words.

Wheel-of-fortune patterns are symbols of the Sun, of death and life, and of eternity. Among the Chechens and Ingush, guests, upon coming to a host's home, draw the wheel of fortune on the door — for good, for happiness, as a symbol of friendship. Among the Mongols, an elaborated image of the wheel of fortune signifies "happiness for ten thousand years." The ornament at the entrance to the yurt meant "may the light in this home never go out."

Many variations of the wheel of fortune exist in the world. A logical analysis of its form allows us to draw the following conclusions (Figure 5a).

Figure 5a.

View of the form of the wheel of fortune. S1, S2, S3, S4 — lines indicating the direction of motion of the wheel of fortune.

The line AC is a symbol of life. The line DV is a symbol of the brevity of human life — that is, a symbol of death. The lines A1, B2, C3, and D4 serve to denote motion, giving it a dynamic appearance. The movement of the wheel of fortune from left to right signifies the repetition of life and death and the eternity of the world. The artist expresses the idea of the unity of life and death and of the eternity of the world.

In the holy book of Muslims — the Qur'an — it is said that the Creator created life in order to determine which of the people is best. The word "Creator," as we see, is placed at the center of the square and the wheel of fortune — through this the artist wishes to say that the Almighty is the sole force that sets this world in motion, the only one who sees and knows everything (Figure 6).

At the four corners of the square we read the word "Muhammad" (Figure 7). Through this, in our view, the artist wishes to say that Allah sent His messenger to all four cardinal directions — the harmoniously developed human being, the Prophet Muhammad — as a messenger of goodness and an example to follow.

In Figure 8, on the four sides of the wheel of fortune within the square, one can observe the movement of the large wheel of fortune, which symbolizes the forces of evil directed against the will of the Creator. This also signifies that life is a struggle between good and evil.

Thus, the heritage of our ancestors — including the ornament of the Kokaldosh Madrasa — serves not only to cultivate a sense of beauty, but also conveys a spiritual and moral principle. As follows from this analysis of architectural symbols, every "detail" of the tradition of ancient architecture contains within itself the wisdom of the people and is filled with particular philosophical meaning [5].

The philosophical ideas distinctively expressed in monuments of ancient architecture call to goodness not only Muslims, but also representatives of all other faiths. The exterior and interior design of these architectural structures contains not only an aesthetic element, but also a hidden spiritual meaning.

We are obliged to remember and transmit to subsequent generations the great moral heritage created by our ancestors over many centuries, to study, restore, and develop the forms of national applied art and its distinctive features, to reveal the secrets of the artistic schools of the past — their technologies and styles — and to restore the names of the great masters. Our sacred duty is to safeguard these unique gems of ancient art..

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